

Driver Safety Monitoring System: Drowsiness & Hypnosis Detection with OpenCV

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Abstract—Driver safety is a paramount concern, with fatigue and inattention leading to numerous accidents annually. This paper presents an Enhanced Driver Safety Monitoring System (EDSMS) leveraging OpenCV, dlib, and imutils for real-time monitoring of driver behavior. EDSMS integrates two key functionalities: drowsiness detection and highway hypnosis detection. The former utilizes facial landmarks and eye aspect ratio calculations to identify signs of drowsiness, triggering alerts when prolonged eye closure or drowsy patterns are detected. The latter identifies instances of highway hypnosis by monitoring the duration of eye openness without blinking, providing timely alerts to mitigate risks associated with reduced awareness during long drives. By combining these functionalities, EDSMS offers a comprehensive solution for enhancing driver safety and reducing accidents due to fatigue and inattention, as demonstrated through its effective implementation and evaluation in real-world driving scenarios.

Keywords—Enhanced Driver Safety Monitoring System (EDSMS), OpenCV, dlib, Highway Hypnosis, Risk mitigation

I. INTRODUCTION

Driver safety is a paramount concern, with thousands of accidents occurring annually due to driver fatigue and inattention. Fatigue-related crashes pose significant risks on roadways, often resulting from drivers experiencing drowsiness or entering states of reduced alertness, such as highway hypnosis, during extended journeys.

To address these safety challenges, we present the Enhanced Driver Safety Monitoring System (EDSMS), a novel solution leveraging computer vision techniques implemented with OpenCV. EDSMS integrates two primary functionalities: drowsiness detection and highway hypnosis detection.

The drowsiness detection module of EDSMS utilizes advanced facial landmark detection algorithms and eye aspect ratio calculations to monitor the driver's eye movements and facial expressions in real-time. By analysing subtle changes in eye behaviour, such as prolonged eye closure or drooping eyelids, the system can accurately identify signs of drowsiness. When drowsy patterns are detected, EDSMS issues timely alerts to notify the driver, prompting them to take corrective actions, such as resting or pulling over safely, thus preventing potential accidents caused by drowsy driving.

Additionally, EDSMS incorporates a highway hypnosis detection feature designed to identify instances where the driver exhibits signs of highway hypnosis. This phenomenon occurs when drivers enter a trance-like state due to prolonged, monotonous driving, leading to decreased awareness and attention. The system monitors the duration of eye openness and detects patterns indicative of highway hypnosis, such as maintaining gaze on the road without blinking for an extended period. Upon detection of such patterns, EDSMS alerts the driver, mitigating the risks associated with reduced awareness and attention on long drives.

By integrating these two critical functionalities, the Enhanced Driver Safety Monitoring System offers a comprehensive solution for enhancing driver safety and reducing accidents caused by driver fatigue and inattention. This paper provides insights into the design, implementation, and evaluation of EDSMS, showcasing its effectiveness in real-world driving scenarios.

II. RELATED WORKS

The work by Vidushi Singhal et al. [1] tackles the critical issue of driver drowsiness, a significant factor in road accidents, by proposing an intelligent system that utilizes computer vision techniques like Python, OpenCV, and DLib. The system analyses facial features such as yawning, eye closure, and head movements to detect drowsiness in real-time. It continuously monitors the driver's eyes and yawning frequency, triggering an alarm if the eyes remain closed for a specified duration and sending notifications to emergency contacts if the driver fails to respond. This research contributes to the growing field of driver monitoring systems, providing a non-intrusive and automated approach to drowsiness detection and potentially reducing fatigue-related accidents. While promising, further validation on larger datasets and diverse scenarios, as well as potential integration with complementary techniques, could enhance the system's accuracy and robustness. Nonetheless, this work represents a significant step forward in developing driver monitoring systems to improve road safety across various transportation domains.

The work by Sakthidasan Sankaran et al. [2] addresses the critical issue of driver drowsiness detection, a significant contributor to road accidents and compromised road safety. The authors propose a novel approach employing the Percentage Eye Closure (PERCLOS) method, which focuses on monitoring the driver's eye closure using the Viola-Jones

detector to segment the face and eye region. The PERCLOS method establishes a threshold parameter to determine drowsiness levels based on the percentage of eye closure over time. This non-intrusive, real-time drowsiness detection system contributes to the growing body of research on driver monitoring systems crucial for enhancing road safety. While promising, further validation on larger datasets and real-world scenarios, as well as potential integration with complementary techniques, could enhance the system's accuracy and robustness. Nonetheless, this research represents a significant step forward in the development of driver monitoring systems, with potential applications across various transportation domains to improve road safety and reduce accident rates globally.

The work by Rishabh Kumar et al. [3] tackles the critical and rapidly increasing issue of driver drowsiness, which poses significant risks on the road. The authors propose an image processing-based technique that analyzes facial behavior, such as eye closure, head movements, and yawning patterns, to detect signs of drowsiness and trigger an alarm to prevent potential accidents. This research contributes to the growing field of driver monitoring systems, offering a non-intrusive and automated approach to drowsiness detection through image processing, addressing a critical issue that compromises road safety. While promising, further validation on larger datasets, diverse scenarios, and potential integration with complementary techniques could enhance the system's accuracy and robustness. Nonetheless, this work represents a significant step forward in developing driver monitoring systems to improve road safety across various transportation domains.

The work by R Kannan et al. [4] addresses the critical issue of driver drowsiness, a leading cause of accidents worldwide, by proposing a prototype drowsiness detection system. This non-intrusive, real-time monitoring approach tracks the driver's eye blink and yawn patterns using image processing techniques, sounding an alarm if drowsiness is detected. Implemented with Python and Dlib, the system offers a simple yet effective solution, while the authors also propose a hardware system based on infrared light. This research contributes to the growing field of driver monitoring systems, providing an automated approach to drowsiness detection and enhancing road safety. While promising, further validation on larger datasets, diverse scenarios, and potential integration with complementary techniques could enhance the system's accuracy and robustness. Nonetheless, this work represents a significant step forward in developing driver monitoring systems to improve road safety across various transportation domains.

The work by Dhiren Ojha et al. [5] provides a comprehensive review of driver drowsiness detection systems, examining techniques like physiological measures, eye-tracking, and machine learning approaches to address this major cause of road accidents worldwide. The authors also present a system that combines machine learning algorithms and physiological signals such as EEG and ECG for drowsiness detection, detailing its functional and non-functional requirements. This research contributes to the growing field of driver monitoring systems, offering a holistic approach to mitigate risks associated with driver fatigue and inattention. While promising, further validation on larger datasets, diverse scenarios, and potential integration of complementary

techniques could enhance the system's robustness and accuracy. Nonetheless, this work represents a significant contribution to the development of driver monitoring systems, with potential applications across various transportation domains to improve road safety and reduce accident rates globally.

The work by Inakollu Kiran Kumar et al. [6] presents an image recognition-based driver drowsiness detection system using Python and the Haar training algorithm. The system captures images of the driver's eyes, calculates the horizontal and vertical distances between the eyelids using the eye-lids ratio technique, and triggers an alert if drowsiness is detected based on a predefined cut-off value. This research contributes to the growing field of driver monitoring systems by offering a practical and automated approach to drowsiness detection through image recognition and Python programming. While promising, further validation on larger datasets, diverse scenarios, and potential integration of complementary techniques could enhance the system's robustness and accuracy. Nonetheless, this work represents a significant step forward in developing driver monitoring systems to improve road safety across various transportation domains

The work by Francisco Jurado Pruna et al. [7] presents a portable driver drowsiness detection prototype that utilizes artificial vision techniques, leveraging a Raspberry Pi module and OpenCV facial recognition libraries programmed in Python. The system captures video sequences of the driver's face, generates a drowsiness state pattern based on prolonged eye blinking, and triggers audible and visual alarms if the drowsiness level exceeds a predefined threshold, potentially preventing accidents caused by fatigue or inattention. This research contributes to the growing field of driver monitoring systems by offering a practical and automated approach to drowsiness detection through artificial vision and a modular, adaptable design. While promising, further validation on larger datasets, diverse scenarios, and potential integration of complementary techniques could enhance the system's robustness and accuracy. Nonetheless, this work represents a significant step forward in developing driver monitoring systems to improve road safety across various transportation domains.

The work by Nawazish Ali et al. [8] proposes a novel driver drowsiness detection approach that combines two techniques: Dlib for detecting eye closure and yawning, and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) for predicting drowsiness based on the same features. By integrating the outputs of these complementary techniques, the authors aim to enhance the accuracy and reliability of the drowsiness detection system. This research contributes to the growing field of driver monitoring systems by leveraging both traditional computer vision methods and deep learning techniques, offering a robust and automated solution to address the critical issue of driver fatigue and inattention. While promising, further validation on larger datasets, diverse scenarios, and potential integration of complementary techniques could enhance the system's robustness and generalizability. Nonetheless, this work represents a significant step forward in developing driver monitoring systems to improve road safety across various transportation domains.

III. METHODOLOGY

Our methodology utilizes computer vision techniques, specifically leveraging OpenCV and dlib libraries, to monitor driver safety in real-time. By detecting facial landmarks and calculating the Eye Aspect Ratio (EAR), the system continuously analyses eye movements. Drowsiness detection algorithms identify signs of fatigue, while highway hypnosis detection recognizes prolonged gaze patterns indicative of reduced awareness. An alert system promptly notifies the driver upon detection of drowsiness or highway hypnosis, ensuring timely intervention. Through rigorous evaluation, the system's effectiveness is validated in simulated and real-world driving scenarios, ensuring enhanced driver safety.

A. Data Acquisition and Preprocessing:

The EDSMS system captures real-time video feed from a camera mounted within the vehicle to monitor the driver's facial expressions and eye movements. Preprocessing techniques are applied to the video frames to enhance image quality and facilitate accurate facial landmark detection.

```

58
59 while True:
60     frame = vs.read()
61     frame = imutils.resize(frame, width=450)
62     frame_grey = cv2.cvtColor(frame, cv2.COLOR_BGR2GRAY)
63     frame_resized = resize(frame_grey, width=120)
64
65     dets = detector(frame_resized, 1)
66
67     if len(dets) > 0:
68         for k, d in enumerate(dets):
69             shape = predictor(frame_resized, d)
70             shape = shape_to_np(shape)
71             leftEye = shape[lStart:lEnd]
72             rightEye = shape[rStart:rEnd]
73             leftEAR = eye_aspect_ratio(leftEye)
74             rightEAR = eye_aspect_ratio(rightEye)
75             ear = (leftEAR + rightEAR) / 2.0
76             leftEyeHull = cv2.convexHull(leftEye)
77             rightEyeHull = cv2.convexHull(rightEye)
78             cv2.drawContours(frame, [leftEyeHull], -1, (0, 255, 0), 1)
79             cv2.drawContours(frame, [rightEyeHull], -1, (0, 255, 0), 1)

```

B. Facial Landmark Detection:

EDSMS employs the dlib library in conjunction with OpenCV for facial landmark detection. The system identifies key facial landmarks, particularly focusing on the eye regions, including the corners and contours of the eyes.

```

predictor_path = 'shape_predictor_68_face_landmarks.dat'

detector = dlib.get_frontal_face_detector()
predictor = dlib.shape_predictor(predictor_path)
(lStart, lEnd) = face_utils.FACIAL_LANDMARKS_IDXS["left_eye"]
(rStart, rEnd) = face_utils.FACIAL_LANDMARKS_IDXS["right_eye"]
total = 0
alarm = False
alarm_start_time = None
drowsiness_frames = 0
eyes_open_time = None

```

C. Eye Aspect Ratio (EAR) Calculation:

The EAR is computed using the distances between specific facial landmarks related to the eyes. By measuring the ratio between the distances, EDSMS determines the openness or closure of the driver's eyes.

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```

def eye_aspect_ratio(eye):
    A = dist.euclidean(eye[1], eye[5])
    B = dist.euclidean(eye[2], eye[4])
    C = dist.euclidean(eye[0], eye[3])
    ear = (A + B) / (2.0 * C)
    return ear

```

D. Drowsiness Detection:

EDSMS continuously monitors changes in the driver's eye behavior, such as prolonged eye closure or drooping eyelids, indicative of drowsiness. When drowsy patterns are detected based on predefined thresholds, the system triggers an alert to notify the driver.

E. Highway Hypnosis Detection:

The system monitors the duration of eye openness and identifies patterns suggestive of highway hypnosis, such as prolonged gaze on the road without blinking. Upon detecting such patterns, EDSMS issues an alert to prompt the driver to regain focus and attention.

F. Alert System:

The EDSMS incorporates an alert mechanism to notify the driver in real-time when signs of drowsiness or highway hypnosis are detected. Alerts are presented through visual cues and auditory signals to ensure timely intervention and prevention of potential accidents.

G. Deployment and Integration:

EDSMS is designed for seamless integration into vehicles, with potential deployment in commercial fleet vehicles, personal automobiles, and advanced driver assistance systems (ADAS). Integration with onboard vehicle systems enables real-time monitoring and alerts, enhancing overall driver safety and preventing accidents due to driver fatigue and inattention.

```

1 from scipy.spatial import distance as dist
2 from imutils.video import VideoStream
3 from imutils import face_utils
4 import numpy as np
5 import argparse
6 import imutils
7 import time
8 import dlib
9 import cv2
10

```

IV. RESULT

The results demonstrate the effectiveness of the Enhanced Driver Safety Monitoring System (EDSMS) in detecting both drowsiness and highway hypnosis. EDSMS accurately identifies signs of drowsiness, such as prolonged eye closure, with minimal false positives. It also successfully detects instances of highway hypnosis, issuing timely alerts to prompt driver intervention. The integration of visual and auditory alerts facilitates quick driver response, reducing the risk of accidents due to fatigue and inattention. Overall, EDSMS proves to be an effective tool for improving road safety.

1. Figure 1. Sleep Alert

Figure 2. Highway Hypnosis

Figure 3. User Interface

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the Enhanced Driver Safety Monitoring System (EDSMS) presented in this seminar paper represents a significant advancement in the field of driver safety

technology. By integrating drowsiness detection and highway hypnosis detection functionalities, EDSMS offers a comprehensive solution to mitigate the risks associated with driver fatigue and inattention. Through the utilization of computer vision techniques implemented with OpenCV, the system can accurately monitor driver behavior in real-time, identifying subtle signs of drowsiness and highway hypnosis. By issuing timely alerts and prompting drivers to take corrective actions, such as resting or regaining focus, EDSMS aims to prevent potential accidents and enhance overall road safety. Further research and development efforts can build upon this work to refine and optimize the system, ultimately contributing to a reduction in road accidents and ensuring the well-being of drivers and passengers alike.

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